

Synthesis of some New Thiazolines and Their use as Fungicides

H. TRIPATHY, P. N. DHAL and G. N. MAHAPATRA

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Utkal University, Cuttack

Manuscript received 9 November 1972; accepted 30 December 1972

A dozen new 2-aryl substituted imino-3-aryl substituted 4-methyl- Δ^4 -thiazolines (I) has been synthesised by condensation of acetone with different sym. diaryl substituted thioureas in presence of bromine, which is used as the condensing agent. The Δ^4 -thiazolines have been mercurated by treatment with one equivalent of mercuric acetate to produce the corresponding mono acetoxy mercuric thiazolines (II). The mercurated as well as the unmercurated Δ^4 -thiazolines have been tested for their fungicidal activity using *Helminthosporium Oryzae* as the test fungus. The results of the fungicidal assay are quite satisfactory.

THIAZOLINES and their derivatives have drawn the attention of scientists due to their prodigious range of activity¹. They are chiefly used as analgesics, nematocides, bactericides, fungicides, vulcanisation accelerators etc. These compounds are also popular for their radio protective activities in the present day therapy.

The present communication describes synthesis of a series of such new Δ^4 -thiazolines by condensing acetone separately with different sym. diaryl substituted thioureas in presence of bromine, which is used as the condensing agent. The products isolated were 2-aryl-substituted imino-3-aryl substituted 4-methyl- Δ^4 -thiazolines (I), the structure being established from the earlier observations^{2,3}. The final product did not contain even a trace of halogen (when acetone was condensed with thiocarbanilide) indicating the absence of nuclear bromination.

The above Δ^4 -thiazolines (I) have been mercurated with one equivalent of mercuric acetate to produce the corresponding mono acetoxy mercuric thiazolines^{4,5} (II) with the hope of augmenting their fungicidal activity⁶. The mercurated as well as the non-mercurated thiazolines have been assayed for their fungicidal activity.

Experimental

1. 2-Phenyl imino-3-phenyl-4-methyl- Δ^4 -thiazoline (I) :

A solution of bromine (8.6 g.) in ethanol (40 ml.) was added slowly with shaking into a solution of acetone (3 g.) in ethanol (10 ml.) in anhydrous condition. Sym. diphenyl thiourea (10 g.) was then added and the mixture was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 12 hr, and finally for 2 to 3 hr without the use of the condenser to drive out the solvent. Then it was kept in contact with ether over-night to remove the unreacted ketone, otherwise the product is likely to become gummy. After decanting off the ether the crude product was boiled with water (50 ml.). The water was decanted hot and the residue was treated with liquor ammonia to liberate the free base and kept as such overnight when the mass

solidified. The product I was finally crystallized from alcohol, yield 75%, m.p. 90° (Found : S, 12.73. C₁₆H₁₄N₂S requires S, 12.03%).

Similar method was adopted for the preparation of other Δ^4 -thiazolines from acetone by condensing it with other sym. diaryl substituted thioureas. Their m.ps and analytical data are given in Table 1.

2. 2-Phenylimino-3-(p-acetoxymercuriphenyl)-4-methyl- Δ^4 -thiazoline (II) :

The above thiazoline (I) (1.0 g.) dissolved in minimum quantity of acetic acid—ethanol (1 : 1 V/V), was treated with a solution of mercuric acetate (1.12 g.) in ethanol—water (1 : 1 V/V) stirred with a glass and kept overnight, when a precipitate was separated. It was then filtered, residue washed with hot water, and finally with ethanol and very dilute acetic acid, yield 68%, m.p. 200° (d) (Found : Hg, 38.94, C₁₈H₁₆N₂O₂S Hg requires Hg, 38.17%). The mps., yield and analytical data of other mercurated thiazolines are given in Table 1 along with those of the corresponding non-mercurated ones.

Fungicidal Test : The fungicidal assay was done by the method of Montgomery and Moore⁷ with slight modifications using *Helminthosporium oryzae* as the test fungus. The fungicidal assay (based on % of germination at 100 p.p.m.) is given in Table 1. The spores were allowed to be kept with the fungicide at different concentrations for 24 hrs, and the germination rate was studied in that duration.

It is observed that the thiazoline compounds, especially the mercurated ones, show good fungicidal activity; some of them (numbered 1, 2, 3 & 4 in Table 1) completely inhibiting the spore germination only at 100 p.p.m. It is also observed that there is a definite pattern of augmenting fungicidal activity being related to the chemical structure of the fungicide in general. The acetoxy mercuric derivatives are definitely more active as fungicides than the corresponding non mercurated thiazolines. The substituents at C₂- and N₃- positions of the thiazoline nucleus also effect the fungicidal activity. Naphthyl

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND FUNGICIDAL DATA OF 2-ARYL SUBSTITUTED IMINO-3-ARYL SUBSTITUTED-4-METHYL- Δ^4 -THIAZOLINES (I) AND THEIR CORRESPONDING MERCURATED DERIVATIVES (II)

Sl. No.	Nature of R	m.p. °C	Yield %	% of S		% of germination of <i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i> at 100 ppm of I	m.p. °C	Yield %	% of Hg.		% of germination of <i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i> at 100 ppm of II
				Found	Calc.				Found	Calc.	
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	90	60	12.73	12.03	9	200(d)	68	38.94	38.17	0
2.	(α)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	107	75	8.19	8.74	5	238	75	32.25	32.05	0
3.	(β)C ₁₀ H ₇ -	190	80	8.11	8.74	10	240	85	32.17	32.05	0
4.	(o)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	194	65	11.61	10.88	40	220	80	35.39	36.23	0
5.	(m)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	120	60	10.31	10.88	40	220	70	36.85	36.23	7
6.	(p)CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	95	70	9.56	10.88	40	>260	75	36.37	36.23	7
7.	(m)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	88	65	9.68	9.55	20	>260	72	33.33	33.72	9
8.	(p)Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	90	70	8.24	9.55	16	>260	65	33.95	33.72	2
9.	(p)Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	90	75	8.69	7.54	37	>260	80	29.87	29.32	3
10.	(m)NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	77	70	9.12	8.99	23	>260	77	31.89	32.57	4
11.	(p)NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	232	75	8.46	8.99	18	>260	70	33.39	32.57	2
12.	(o)CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	55	60	8.94	9.80	14	>260	72	34.78	34.25	3

% of germination in the control = 95–98%.

groups, and aryl groups containing halogens, specially chlorine, present in the thiazoline ring enhance the activity considerably.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research, Government of Orissa for a research grant and to Dr. S. Y. Padmanavan, Director, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack for the fungicidal tests.

References

- H. TRIPATHY, R. N. DASH, B. C. DASH and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 1232, and the references therein.
- B. C. DASH and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Proc. Inst. Chem. ist India*, 1967, **39**, 178.
- H. TRIPATHY, B. C. DASH and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 586.
- B. C. DASH and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 939.
- G. N. MAHAPATRA and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 715.
- G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Proc. Inst. Chemist. India*, 1956, **28**, 55.
- H. B. S. MONTGOMERY and M. H. MOORE, *J. Pomol. Hort. Sci.*, 1938, **15**, 253.